

AMELIORATIVE EFFECT OF AEROBIC TRAINING ON FEV/FVC RATIO OF ASTHMATIC ADULTS IN SANGA AND JEMA'A LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREAS OF KADUNA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: This study examined ameliorative effect of aerobic training on forced expiratory volume/ forced vital capacity ratio of asthmatic adults in Sanga and Jemaa local government areas of Kaduna state, Nigeria. One group repeated trials research design, in which the subjects were given different treatments at different times. In the design, participants underwent aerobic training of 40 – 50 % maximal heart rate (RPE) for a minimum of 20 minutes during the training session conducted in three (3) alternate days per week for twelve (12th) weeks. A total of 30 asthmatic adults attending the Gwantu General Hospital, General Hospital Kafanchan, and College Clinic at the respiratory units volunteered to participate in this study. Out of the 30, 26 met the inclusion criteria and were assigned to the aerobic training; since there were no control group and the baseline values served as the control. The aerobic group engaged in treadmill walk at intensities ranging between 40% - 50% of estimated HR max. The training given was at a moderate intensity of 40 -50% maximal heart beat (MHR) (1 -4 weeks) which was increased progressively from 51 – 60 % HRMax (5 – 8 weeks) and 61 – 70% HR max (9 -12 weeks). The data collected were statistically analyzed using descriptive statistics to determine means, standard deviation and standard error, repeated measures analysis of variance (ANOVA II) was used to determine significant difference and a post-hoc Scheffe's test to determine where significant difference occurred, using a level of significance of 0.05. The result of the study revealed that aerobic training programs caused an increase $p < 0.05$ in FEV/FVC ratio. It was concluded that asthmatic adults should participate in aerobic training regularly in order to control their asthma episodes (attacks). Health professionals and fitness centers should use this method of training for asthmatic patients and should be encouraged to exercise themselves at least 20 – 40 minutes in a week to improve their pulmonary functions.

Introduction

Asthma is a serious global health problem that affects people of all ages. According to Center for Disease Control and Prevention (2011), the

disease is broadly distributed by sex, age, ethnicity and geographical location and remains the most chronic disease in adults and children worldwide. The causes of asthma are unknown

(Ayuk, Liloh & Oguonu, 2010). However, heredity, allergens and environmental factors (namely, aspirin, dust pollutants and emotion) play a role and can be divided into the following categories: Extrinsic asthma-allergen-induced, mediated by an immune system reaction, aspirin asthma-non allergic cause found and mixed asthma-cause by more than one factor. Asthma occurs in 5-12% of the population worldwide at any age but is most common in childhood and reduces at puberty. In some instances, the incidence increases as people get older. Asthma runs in families with other allergic conditions, suggesting a general atopic constitution (genetic predisposition) associated with chromosomes 5 and 11 (Eveson & Pompell, 2010). Early onset indicates an allergic basis for the disease. Atopic asthma is common cause for treatment resistant asthma in children. This type of the disease occurs in 30-50% of the general population. In the USA, asthma prevalence increased to 60% in children and 45% in adults between 1980-1999 (Desalu, .O.O, Busari, Onyedum, C.C, Iseh, K.R, Salawu, F.K & Salami, A.K. (2011). These disease conditions increased the resistance to airflow, show the rate at which air can be forced out of the lungs and increases the contraction of smooth muscle in the bronchioles. It also induces changes in the lung tissue that result in the destruction of the alveolar walls, collapse of the bronchioles and decreased elasticity of the lung tissue (National Asthma Education and Prevention program, 2013). The collapsed bronchioles increase the resistance to air-flow. People with asthma could suffer from chronic bronchitis. This is because

the air passages are inflamed, swelling increases mucus secretion and gradual loss of cilia result in narrowed bronchioles and an increased resistance to air-flow. (Wu, X., Gao, S., & Lian, Y. (2020).

An asthma attack is the result of an orderly sequence of events that can be initiated by wide variety of factors. For instance, in mast cells, one of the cells that is part of the bronchial tubes it is believed that a variety of factors such as dust, chemicals, antibodies and exercise initiate an asthma attack by increasing calcium ion (Ca^{++}) influx into the cell, causing a release of chemical mediators such as histamine and a special chemical that attracts white blood cells (Monoharan & Swaminathan, 2009). The mediator in turn triggers the following effects: increase smooth muscle contraction (via an elevation of Ca^{++} in the muscle cell) leading to bronchoconstriction, initiation of a bronchoconstriction reflex response via the vagus nerve and causing an inflammation response (swelling of tissue) (Fawibe et al, 2011).

Views on the pathogenic mechanisms of asthma have changed with the recognition that chronic inflammation underlines the syndrome. A genetic background sets the stage for a cytokine imbalance that promotes the formation of IgE (immunoglobulin E).

Previously, it was thought that abnormal contractility of the air-way smooth muscle gave rise to variable overflow obstruction-responsible for the common symptoms of wheezing and shortness of breath. For many years, researchers also assumed that mast cell mediators played the critical role in the patho-physiology (Zeng,

Q., Liao, W., Fang, W., Liu, S., Duan, C., Dai, Y., & Wei, C. (2023). Recent research, however, established that asthma, even in its mildest form involves the activation of many different inflammatory cells in the asthmatic airways. Inflammatory cells produce a variety of mediators, in particular mast cells, eosinophils and T-lymphocytes which act on target cells of the airways to produce the typical features of asthma (Onyedum, Desalu, Nwosu & Ezeudo, 2012). The inflammatory process leads to airway hyperactivity, plasma exudation, mucus secretion and the activation of neural mechanisms (Adeyeye & Onadeko, 2008). Airway obstruction occurs due to spasm of the bronchial muscle, oedema of the airway, increased mucus production, cellular infiltration and subsequently injury to the epithelium. Classic symptomatic features are wheezing, increased shortness of breath, coughing and chest tightness. Tightness can sometimes be the only effect some people complain of especially in young healthy adults. It was reported by Ayuk et al, (2010) that chronic inflammation leads to structural changes such as an increase in airway smooth muscle and irreversible fibrosis (Venkartewarlu, 2011). There is also increased evidence that transcription factors such as nuclear factor kappa B play a pivotal role in the expression of inflammatory genes in asthma. Epidemiological studies linked IgE antibodies to the severity of asthma when inhaled allergens encounter the dendritic cells that line the airway, this stimulates dendritic cells to migrate to draining lymph nodes and present the processed antigen to the T- and B-Lymphocytes

(Onyedum et al, 2012). Interactions between these cells elicit responses that are influenced by cytokines and co-stimulating molecules. Mast cells are stimulated to release histamine and leutrienes, responsible for airway smooth muscle constriction. After four to six hours, however, a prolonged phase of airflow obstruction may follow, because of cytokines and chemokins generated by resident inflammatory cells. This is known as the late asthmatic phase that illustrates the danger in the situations where an asthma sufferer is not observant and gets caught off guard, especially during the night or early morning. Decline in lung function occurs in all people, but even more so with age in adults with asthma. Previous researches on asthmatic non-smokers in Australia showed a decline of 50ml/year in FEV_i compared to 35ml/year in controls. This was confirmed by the Copenhagen Heart Study with values 38ml/year and 22ml/year respectively (Kolawale et al, 2011), Sedentary lifestyle can cause the deterioration of respiratory indices. The interventions, such as physical activity programs, might prevent such deterioration (Shadmehri, S., Kazemi, N., & Heydari, F. Z. (2021), Lorenzo-Capellá, I., Ramos-Álvarez, J. J., Jiménez-Herranz, E., Maffulli, N., Iuliano, E., Padulo, J., & Calderón-Montero, F. J. (2025). Spirometry test are normally carried out to assess how an individual inhales or exhales volume of air over a period of time. It also measures how fast one can blow air out, and is used as a screening test for respiratory health (Zeng et al, 2023). The most important variables

measured in spirometry are volumes of flow of air in the lungs. This provides important information about the presence of any restrictive or obstructive lung disorder, which helps in measuring the effect of the disorder on pulmonary functions, assessing prognosis and screening individuals at risk of having pulmonary disease as well as assessing response to treatment (Center for Disease Control and prevention, 2011).

Injury and repair restores normal function, the same is not true for chronic inflammation. In asthma, the process of chronic inflammation may lead to altered structure called remodeling of the airways. Remodeling entails thickening of the airways walls with increases in sub-mucosal tissue, the adventitia and smooth muscle. The claim is that the training improves respiratory power and breathing mechanics by strengthening the respiratory muscles through breathing resistance provided by the training method (Jacobson, 2022), (Ma, Q., Lu, M., Yang, Q., Gong, F., Zhou, L., & Xu, D. 2025)

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

It is estimated that 300 million people are affected with bronchial asthma. Zeng, Q., Liao, W., Fang, W., Liu, S., Duan, C., Dai, Y., & Wei, C. (2023) maintained that the prevalence of asthma is variable and more prevalent in developed countries with higher rates recorded in Australia, United Kingdom and New Zealand. According to the Center for Disease Control and Prevention (2011), more than eighteen million, seven hundred and ninety-three thousand, nine hundred and forty-six (18,793,946) adults living in the United States have been diagnosed with

the disease. Over the past few decades, the incidence and severity of the disease continue to rise among adults. Asthma prevalence rate among adults between 18-65 for a decade nearly doubled from 3.6% to 7.5% from 1980 through 1995, currently 12.7% of all adults receive asthma diagnoses sometime in their life (Desalu, .O.O, Salami, A.K, Fawibe,A.E, & Salami.A.K (2012). According to World Health Organization (2020) data on asthma, Nigeria ranked 37th in the world between 2000-2009 with an extrapolated statistics of 12,575,356. Asthma deaths in Nigeria reached 10,871 (0.64%) of total deaths with the age adjusted death rate of 15.55 per 100,000 of the population. In Nigeria, the prevalence of asthma also ranges from 7% to 18% in the general population (Desalu. Salami & Fawibe, 2010; Kolawale et al; 2011) reported that out of 96,000 paediatric outpatients attendees admitted each year, 3% were found to have severe asthma during a period of 4 years in Zaria, Northern Nigeria where Sanga and Jemaa local Governments are part of. Asthmatics should participate in exercise to fully gain the numerous health benefits exercise has to offer. With millions of people being affected by asthma, a significant percentage of Nigerian adults are likely to be affected and could suffer from mortality. The resultant effect of this on the quality of life of Nigerian adults living with asthma is quite alarming. These impaired pulmonary functions are associated with increased mortality and morbidity. This is a national concern due to the impact asthma has on the well-being of Nigerian adult population.

One of the greatest obstacles in the fight against asthma is judgmental errors and misconceptions about asthma, which has affected patient's willingness to combine pharmacological and non-pharmacological interventions, especially exercise. (Murugesan, N., Saxena, D., Dileep, A., Adrish, M., & Hanania, N. A., 2023)

The current study is thus aimed at determining the ameliorative effect of aerobic training on FEV/FVC ratio of asthmatic adults in Sanga and Jemaa Local Government Areas of Kaduna State, Nigeria.

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a quasi-experimental research design as suggested by Kerlinger (1988). In this design, one group was given different treatments at different times. The baseline or pre-training measures serves as control, while the 4th week, 8th week and 12th week measures served the experimental manipulations. The design was to maximize the error residual variance, identify between units variance and to maximize the error residual variance. In this design, 26 asthmatic adults (13 males and 13 female) between 18 – 35 years volunteered underwent aerobic training at a moderate intensity of 40 – 50% of maximal heart rate (HRmax) for a minimum of 20 minutes in a training session, conducted on 3 alternate days a week(Monday, Wednesday and Friday) for 12th weeks. The participants in this study had no contra-indication to participate in the aerobic training. The population for the study consisted of 30 asthmatic adults, attending the out-patient

Respiratory Unit at the General Hospital Kafanchan, General Hospital Gwantu, and Kaduna State College of Education Gidan Waya Clinic between the ages of 18 and 35 years.

The purposive sampling technique was used to categorize the subjects according to levels of asthmatic attack as mild, moderate and severe episodes. In this study, 26 volunteered asthmatic adults were drawn from the population, which comprised 13 males and 13 females drawn from the out-patient Respiratory Unit of at the General Hospital Kafanchan, General Hospital Gwantu, and Kaduna State College of Education Gidan Waya Clinic. The subjects were classified into three groups according to the severity of the disease. This grading system was modified from the one described by Charity & Vijay (2011). This severe group consisted of zero (0) patients with more than 10 acute attacks a year with or without complete clinical recovery between attacks. The moderate group consisted of thirteen (13) those with 5 attacks a year and usually show complete or partial freedom from wheezing between attacks, while the mild group have thirteen (13) with 1 attacks a year with complete clinical recovery between attacks.

All subjects were screened to ensure that they met the following inclusion criteria before they were selected for this study:

- i. They were all asthmatic outpatients from out-patient Respiratory Unit at the General Hospital Kafanchan, General Hospital Gwantu, and Kaduna State College of Education Gidan Waya Clinic.

- ii. They were all from the mild and moderate groups of complete clinical recovery between attacks.
- iii. They were all between the ages of 18 and 35 years for both men and women
- iv. They were all taking inhaled bronchodilator and other medications for asthma (inhaler).
- v. They were all to perform the walking test which was used for the purpose of aerobic training.

The following instruments were used in the study for data collection: Treadmills Trimline 7800 Treadmill, USA was used for aerobic training, Spirometer: A digital Spirometer SP 10, CE0123, manufactured by Contect Medical Systems Co. Ltd China, was used for pulmonary function test, and stop watch: Six stop watches Digital Port-Spring Model 015, manufactured by Jewele Sport Company, Britain was used for monitoring duration of the aerobic training (Ishee, 2012).

To be able to conduct the test for this study, ethic approval to use human subjects for the study was granted by the Ahmadu Bello University Committee on Use of Human Subjects for Research (ABUCUHSR) Zaria.

Subject's physical characteristics (height and weight) were assessed in accordance with the protocol of International Working Group on Anthropometry (IWGK) as described by Atlantis, Martins, Helen & Taylor, (2009). Specifically, measurements include standing height and weight. Subject's height were measured, while standing erect looking straight ahead and bare-footed against the stadiometer.

Horizontal broad blade wooden ruler was rested on the head of each subject against the instrument to the nearest 0.1cm. Subject's weight was measured using a portable bathroom scale with provision for re-calibration while dressed in light dress without footwear. The weight was recorded to the nearest 0.5kg. The height and weight measures was used to calculate the body mass index using the Quelled index by dividing weight (kg) by height (m) squared (wt/ht) (Uchechukwu & Chukwunoso, 2010). The BMI values were read off a monogram for BMI (Dorth, Arnt, Eli-Anne, Stian & Tomas, 2010).

Each subject was asked to be in a sitting position (upright sitting position) and was expected to wear the spirometer with a nose clip on. They were instructed to take maximum inspiration and blow air forcefully into the mouth piece of the spirometer as rapidly as forcefully and completely as possible. It was ensured that a tight seal was maintained between the lips and mouth piece of the Spirometer. The best of three trials was recorded for each subject expressed in liters of body temperature and ambient pressure saturated with water vapour (American Thoracic Society, 2005). Forced expiratory vital capacity (FEVC) is the volume of air that can be expired rapidly with a maximum inspiration. Forced expiratory volume in one second (FEV₁) is the volume of air expired in the first second of maximal expiration after a maximal inspiration and is a useful measure of how quickly full lungs can be emptied. It represents the volume of air expired in the first second of a FVC. Estimation

of FEV_i is the most commonly used screening test for airway diseases. Normally, FEV₁ is about 80% of the FVC (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (2011); Ishee, (2012). It is useful in distinguishing between restrictive and obstructive diseases. Peak expiratory flow rate (PEFR) is the highest flow value measured during forced expiration. It is one of the many tests that measured how well the airways work. It measures airway obstructions and it will detect moderate or severe disease. Factors which determine PEFR are airway obstruction, closure and compression of small airways, strength of expiratory muscles and the lung and chest mechanic (Shadmehri, S., Kazemi, N., & Heydari, F. Z. (2021).

Peak expiratory flow (PEF) is the fastest rate at which air can move through the airways during a forced expiration starting with fully inflated lung. Most adults and children, even as young as 5 years of age, can perform a PEF measurement. The effort required to produce measurement is short maximal blast of air. The peak flow varies according to age, sex and height. PEF monitoring is an important clinical tool at home, in the office emergency department and Hospital (Roucell, 2011). PEF can be used for diagnosis if the PEF increases more than 15 percent. 15 to 20 minutes after inhalation of rapid acting β 2-agonist, or PEF varies more than 20 percent from morning measurement upon arising to measurement 12 hours. Later (more than 10 percent in patients who are not taking a bronchodilator) or PEF decreases 15 percent after 6 minutes of sustained running or exercise. It is important to establish personal

value and minimum circulation variability (Zeng, et al, 2023).

Each subject will be made to sit in an upright position, the spirometer worn with the mouth clip piece tightly and took a short maximal blast of air. The best of three trials shall be recorded for each subject expressed in liters at body temperature and ambient pressure with water vapour.

Training Protocol

All exercise training sessions were preceded by 10 minutes warm up and exercises including juggling and stretching exercises. 15 minutes was used for interval running in the first 4 weeks, 20 minutes in the second weeks of training and 25 minutes in the last 4 weeks of training which ended with cool-down sessions. The training session for this research lasted 12 weeks and was done between 4.30 pm – 6.00 pm three times a week (that is Monday, Wednesday and Friday). All participants were engaged in brisk treadmill walk/jogging at a speed of one km/h at a gradient of 0% for the first four weeks. The gradient was increased later to 1% due to improved aerobic fitness and to correlate with outdoor walking and to compensate for the lack of air resistance. The speed of the treadmill was gradually increased by 0.5km/hr or 1km/hr depending on the fitness level of the subjects (Cooper, C.B (2009); Rowel, 2011).

The participants started training at an intensity of 40-50% of HR_{max} from the baseline to 4th week. It was increased to 51 – 60% intensity in the 5th – 8th week and was increased to an intensity of 61 – 70% HR_{max} in the 9th – 12th week (Raul, Manuel, Sean and Ana, 2010). This

gradual increase of training duration was followed in order to allow the subjects to adapt to the stress of training. However, the training period was altered depending on the rate of perceived physical exertion (PPE) of the participants using the modified Borg scale. The scale rates from 6 – 20; where 6 stands for “no” exertion at all’, while 20 stands for “maximal

exertion” in order to permit optimal adaptation to the aerobic training (Borg, G.V. & Linderholm, H. 1998). The data collected in this study were statistically analyzed, using the statistical package of the Social Science (SPSS) version 16, using 0.05 alpha level of significance, and the results of which are presented and discussed below:

Results

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of physical characteristics of respondents after 4th week, 8th, 9th week and 12th week of training (n = 26).

Variable	Duration of training	Mean	SD	SE
Age(years)	Baseline	24.62	6.57	2.34
Weight(kg)		75.34	5.57	2.56
Height(m)		1.68	0.78	0.21
BMI (kg/m ²)		26.55	1.99	0.44
Weight(kg)	4 th week	74.23	4.56	1.33
BMI(kg)		26.25	2.23	0.87
Weight(Kg)	8 th week	71.33	1.42	1.67
BMI(kg/m ²)		26.02	1.68	.68
Weight(kg)	12 th week	70.55	4.45	1.54
BMI(kg/m ²)		25.43	1.99	.45

MBI = body mass, kg= 70.55, kg/m² =25.43

Table 2 shows the means,(SD) and (SE) of the physical characteristics of the subjects used 24.62 ± 6.57, 75.342 ± 1.68 ± 0.78 and 26.55 ± 1.99 kg/m² respectively. The result of the BMI at baseline showed that the subjects were overweight. As training progressed, the mean weight and BMI of the subjects reduced after 8th week 71.33 ± 1.42 and 26.02 ± 1.68 respectively. Further decrease was observed also after 12th

week in weight and BMI, (70.55 ± 4.45 and 25.43 ± 1.99 kg/m²) for this study. An observation of the baseline data showed that the average age, weight, height and body mass index (BMI) of the participants were respectively due to aerobic training.

Sub-hypothesis IV: There is no significant effect of aerobic training on FEV/FVC ratio of asthmatic adults in Sanga and Jemaa Local Government Areas of Kaduna State, Nigeria.

To test this sub-hypothesis, information regarding the effect of aerobic training on

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of means, SD, and SE of Aerobic Fitness FEV/FVC ratio of asthmatic adults over the duration of the training.

Variable	Duration of training	Mean	SD	SE	% change
FEV/FVC Ratio	Baseline	2.4623	.13023	.02564	
	4 th week	1.6996	.39174	.07683	
	8 th week	1.1523	.47474	.09310	1.31 = 53.20%
	12 th week	.9423	.54129	.10616	1.52 = 61.73%

Table 2 above shows the means, SD and SE of FEV/FVC ratio of asthmatic adults in Sanga and Jemaa Local Govt. Areas in Kaduna State, Nigeria at 0 week, (baseline), immediately after 4th week, 8th week, and 12th week of aerobic training of asthmatic adults in Sanga and Jemaa loc govt. areas. An observation of the baseline data (0 week) showed that the participants had means values of FEV/FVC ratio of 2.4623 ± 0.13073. Further observation of the table also

Table 3. Repeated Measure Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on FEV/FVC ratio of asthmatic adults by weeks of training.

Source	SS	DF	MS	F	Sig.
Corrected model	36.674	3	12.225	71.189	.000
Intercept	255.753	1	255.753	1.4893*	.000
Training	36.674	3	12.225	71.189**	.000
Error	17.172	100	.172		
Total	309.600	104			
Corrected total	53.847	103			

F (3,104) = 2.00 P < 0.05

** Significant *Not Significant

FEV/FVC ratio of asthmatic adults in Sanga and Jemaa Local Government Areas, Nigeria before, during and after training is presented in the descriptive statistical Table 4.2.5a

revealed that mean values of FEV/FVC ratio of asthmatic adults after 4th week were 1.6996 ± .39174, 1.1523 ± .47474 and .9423 ± .54129 liters after 4th week, 8th week and 12th week respectively.

In order to find out whether the increase were statistically significant, the data were analyzed using repeated measures analysis ANOVA, the result of which is presented in table 3.2b;

Table 3.2b shows the results of repeated measures ANOVA on FEV/FVC ratio of asthmatic adults in Sanga and Jemaa Local Government Areas, Nigeria at baseline, 4th week, 8th week and 12th week of aerobic training. An observation of the results revealed that training had significant effect on FEV/FVC ratio. However, a comparison of baseline and 12th week values showed no significant effect on intercept (P.000). Therefore, the null

hypothesis which states that there is no significant effect of aerobic training on FEV/FVC ratio of asthmatic adults in Sanga and Jemaa Local Govt. Areas is hereby rejected.

To establish which phase of training was responsible for the significant difference, post-hoc Scheffe's tests was applied on the means at baseline, 4th week, 8th week, and 12th week, the result of which is presented in table 4.2c

Table 4:2c Results of Scheffe's post-hoc tests on the mean of FEV/FVC ratio of the subjects before, during and after training periods.

(1)Week	(J Week) Mean difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Interval Lower Bound	Upper bound
Baseline	4 th week	.76269	.22511	.000	.4354	1.0900
	8 th week	1.31000**	.22511	.000	.9827	1.6373
	12 th week	1.52000	.22511	.000	1.1927	1.8473
4 th week	Baseline	-.76269	.32510	.014	-1.0900	-.4354
	8 th week	.54731	.32510	.000	.2200	.8746
	12 th week	.75731	.32510	.022	.4300	1.0846
8 th week	Baseline	-1.31000**	.43512	.024	-1.6373	-.9827
	4 th week	-.54731	.43512	.000	-.8746	-.2200
	12 th week	.21000	.43512	.349	-1.173	.5373
12 th week	Baseline	-1.52000**	.11527	.000	-1.8473	-1.1927
	4 th week	-.75731	.11527	.000	-1.0846	-.4300
	8 th week	-.21000	.11527	.349	-.5373	.1173
	12 th week	.76269	.11527	.000	.5343	.9911

Baseline Vs 4th week, Baseline Vs 8th week and baseline vs 12th week. **Significant

Table 4.2c Shows the significant difference in the means of FEV/FVC ratio of asthmatic adults was due to the mean difference of baseline Vs. 4th week, baseline Vs 8th week, and baseline vs 12th week (sig 0.000) less than P > 0.05.

Discussion of findings

The purpose of the study was to examine the effect of aerobic training on FEVI/FVC ratio of asthmatic adults in Sanga and Jemaa Local Government Areas of Kaduna State, Nigeria. To achieve this therefore, twenty-six (26) asthmatic adults of mean age 24.62 years, mean weight 75.34kg and mean height 1.68m and mean BMI

26.55kg/m² at baseline were adjudged to meet the criteria for asthmatic adults required for the study. Results of the study showed that significant difference existed in the mean values of FEVI/FVC ratio of asthmatic adults in Sanga and Jemaa on the account of the period of training. The mean of FEV/FVC were 2.4623, 1.6996, 1.1523 and .9423 in their week 0, 4th week, 8th week and 12th weeks respectively. This shows that the higher the period of training, the higher the increase of the FEVI/FVC ratio of the asthmatic adults. This result agrees with the findings of the study carried out by Turquetto, A. L. R., Dos Santos, M. R., Agostinho, D. R., Sayegh, A. L. C., de Souza, F. R., Amato, L. P., & Jatene, M. B. (2021), Shadmehri, S., Kazemi, N., & Heydari, F. Z. (2021), Jacobson, B. (2022), Indriani, F., Rahmawati, N. A., & Irawan, D. S. (2025) who observed a significant change in FEVI/FVC ratio following exercise administration in asthmatic patients. Contrary to the study of Riza & Farid (2005) who demonstrated that there was no significant change in FEVI/FVC ratio of subjects suffering from asthma. The difference in their results may be attributed to the fact that airway disorders such as asthma, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and bronchitis cause obstructive type of lung function abnormality. This is diagnosed by reduced FEVI > FVC percent less than 75% and FEVI % predicted less than 80%.

This finding may be attributed to the regular physical activity especially the observation that aerobics strengthen respiratory muscles, thereby resulting in an increase in lung capacity Jacobson, B. (2022), Lommatzsch, M.,

Brusselle, G. G., Levy, M. L., Canonica, G. W., Pavord, I. D., Schatz, M., & Virchow, J. C. (2023), Malinovschi, A., Rydell, N., Fujisawa, T., Borres, M. P., & Kim, C. K. (2023) and Neves, R. V. P., Corrêa, H. L., Reis, A. L., Andrade, R. V., Araújo, T. B., Santos, R. L., ... & dos Santos Rosa, T. (2024).. However, this is opposed by the findings of Dencker, Thorsson, Karlsson, Linden, Svenson, Wollmer, and Andersen, (2006): who found out that exercise exposed individuals suffering from chronic obstructive pulmonary diseases are prone to psychological problems including anxiety and depression due to decrease in their ability to inhale air because of narrowed airways. The changes in the psychological variables are very important in the long run given that the person's willingness to continue the exercise program is a major factor determining the rate of decline during the course of the disease (Ishee, 2012). It was reported in Dikki(2009) that as one ages however, structural changes occur that impede the ventilatory response which include a loss of elastic recoil, chest wall become stiffer resulting to reduced lung capacity. Since breathlessness is usually a transient symptom during exercise, patients should slow down rather than stop the exercise suddenly.

The present study also revealed that aerobic exercise caused an increase in FEVI/FVC ratio and PEFr. This is in agreement with the findings of Turquetto, A. L. R., Dos Santos, M. R., Agostinho, D. R., Sayegh, A. L. C., de Souza, F. R., Amato, L. P., ... & Jatene, M. B. (2021). Rajaure, Y. S., Thapa, B., Budhathoki, L., Rana, S. R., & Khadka, M. (2023), Du, Y., Jiang, K., & Li, H. (2024) and

Vamja, D. P., Amin, M. B., &Horo, P. (2025), who demonstrated that there was improvement in the pulmonary functions of asthmatic athletes. However, in a study conducted by Alexander, Oni, Erhabor &Egbagbe (2010) showed that asthma restrict patients from engaging in sports and physical activity. It was also found to disturb sleep and was responsible for recurrent hospitalization in 50 % of the patients. The reason for this may be because the majority of the patients studied in this study preferred the use of aerosol bronchodilator for treatment of asthma, instead of combining it with exercise.

Conclusion

This study investigated the Ameliorative effect of aerobic training on forced expiratory volume of asthmatic Patients in Kaduna State College of Education, Gidan Waya, Nigeria, revealed that aerobic training has significant increase in forced expiratory volume with a value of (1.40)73.75% of asthmatic patients based on the duration of training.

Recommendations

On the basis of the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made to improve the quality of life of young asthmatic Patients in

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1. Participation in aerobic training has been shown to increase functional capacity of asthmatic adults. Therefore, asthmatic adults should be enlightened through seminars and workshops to combine both pharmacological treatments with exercise.
2. Since aerobic training was found to improve pulmonary functions of asthmatic patients, it is suggested that health professionals and fitness centers should use this method of training for asthmatic patients and they should be encouraged to exercise themselves for at least 20-40 minutes only in a week to improve their quality of life.
3. In view of the beneficial role of exercise training for health in the asthmatic patients, it is recommended that asthmatic adults should personally engage in regular walking/jogging as a prophylactic measure against pulmonary dysfunction.

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